

Research

Quality Care of Peripheral IV-line Insertion and Its Impact on Patient Outcomes: A Cross-Sectional Study

Imad Majeed ¹, Shafaq Saleem ^{2#}, Maaz Ullah ³, Arooba Khan ³, Mahnoor Khatak ³, Sarah Rahman ², Muhammad Haroon ², Lubna Meraj ⁴

1. Department of Infectious Diseases, University of Louisville, Louisville, Kentucky, USA
2. Department of Medicine, Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
3. Department of Medicine, Khyber Teaching Hospital, Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, Pakistan
4. Department of Medicine Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan

Abstract:**Background:**

Peripheral intravenous catheters (PIVCs) are widely used in hospitalized patients, yet they are often associated with complications due to suboptimal insertion and maintenance practices. This study aimed to evaluate the quality of PIVC care and its impact on patient outcomes in tertiary hospitals in Pakistan.

Methods:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted over three months in the medical wards of Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar and Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi. Data were collected from 280 patients using a validated semi-structured questionnaire targeting nurse practices, patient education, and procedural adherence. Statistical analysis, including chi-square tests, assessed associations between practice variables and clinical outcomes.

Results:

The results of the participants, 60% were female and the mean age was 48.1 ± 19.5 years. Nurses inserted 93.6% of PIVCs. Although 78.6% obtained informed consent, only 60.7% adequately explained the procedure. Aseptic technique was followed in 82.9% of cases, and appropriate cannula size and site were pre-assessed in 89.3%. However, 75.7% of patients were not assessed 48 hours post-removal. First-attempt cannulation success was significantly associated with appropriate site and size selection ($p < 0.05$) and the inserter's role ($p = 0.03$).

Conclusion:

While basic guidelines for PIVC insertion were often followed, gaps in patient communication, documentation, and post-removal assessment persist. Improving nurse training and institutional protocols may reduce complications and improve vascular access outcomes.

Keywords: Peripheral Intravenous Catheters; Intravenous Therapy; PIVC; Pakistan

Corresponding Author: shafaqsaleem6@gmail.com

Introduction

Peripheral intravenous catheters (PIVCs) are among the most commonly used intravascular devices in hospitals, as up to 80% of hospitalized patients require intravenous (IV) therapy [1]. They are usually inserted into the superficial veins of the forearm and hand, with longer lengths available for accessing deeper vessels. Thus they offer a quick and low-cost method for the establishment of vascular access [2].

PIVCs continue to be essential for medical treatment administration; however, not without certain complications, which may include dislodgment and blockage of the catheter, leakage and extravasation of catheter contents, infections of the surrounding tissues, including cellulitis, phlebitis, and various soft tissue infections [3]. One of the most grave complications associated with the use of a peripheral intravenous catheter is a catheter-associated bloodstream infection [4]. Even though PIVCs are not meant for

long term vascular access of more than 2-7 days, however PIVCs may have to be removed prematurely due to complications [5]. A lack of knowledge and skill amongst healthcare practitioners regarding PIVC insertion and care has been recognized as one of the main factors leading to catheter failure and its premature removal [6]. Various studies have assessed and identified deficits in healthcare personnel's education skills and practices regarding catheter and site selection, timely complication identification and overall adherence to recognized guidelines [7, 8]. Nurses insert more than 71 % of PIVCs and thus they have a major role in the timely prevention and control of PIVC related complications and infections [9]. Subpar nursing care at Day 1 was significantly associated with the development of PIVC induced phlebitis [10]. Furthermore, difficulties achieving successful peripheral vascular access begin at the moment of insertion as first-attempt PIVC insertion failure rates can be up to 25% for adults upto 50% for children [11].

Considering the influence that healthcare practitioners have over the successful insertion and maintenance of PIVCs and the reduction of PIVC-related complications, strict, guideline-based practice is imperative. Hence further research to assess the implementation of these practices may help curb failure and complication rates. The rationale of this study was to assess the quality of care in peripheral IV line insertion and its overall impact on patient-related outcomes.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on patients admitted to the medical wards of Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar, and Behnazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan. The study was conducted over three months from October to December 2022, following approval of the research proposal from the Ethical Review Board of Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar, Pakistan, under Reference Number 6295. A sample size of 280 participants was determined using Cochran's formula, assuming a 95% confidence level ($Z = 1.96$) and a margin of error of 8.25%, with an estimated prevalence of 50% to ensure a conservative estimate. A convenient sampling technique was used. The inclusion criteria consisted of patients who had consented to the study and were ≥ 18 years of age, to whom PIVC were inserted for clinical care for predicted > 24 hours, and to whom PIVC were indicated for administration of IV fluids, total parental nutrition, Blood/Blood products, intravenous drug therapy, inotropic support, and pre-procedure venous access. Exclusion criteria consisted of patients who did not consent to the study, in whom PIVC was placed under emergency conditions, patients with laboratory-confirmed bloodstream infection within the prior 48 hours, patients with a coexistent catheter (PIVC intravenous midline, peripherally inserted central catheter, or central venous catheter), those who received end-of-life care, and those who were cognitively barrier to consent. After obtaining informed consent, a validated semi-structured questionnaire was used to assess nurses' knowledge and practice regarding the care and maintenance of peripheral intravenous cannulas, patient information and education, indications and contraindications of intravenous cannulas, and quality care-related questions, which were answered directly by staff nurses and patients. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS24. The mean and standard deviation for age were calculated. Additionally, frequency and percentages for gender, indications, contraindications, pre and post-assessment insertion care, informed consent before cannula insertion, information and education of the patient, documentation of the date/time, aseptic technique, appropriate size and site of the cannula, unsuccessful attempts, insertion records, and the person passing the IVCs were calculated. The chi-square test was conducted with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, considering a p-value of <0.05 as statistically significant.

Results

A total of 280 patients participated in the study. There were 112 males (40%) and 168 females (60%). The mean (average) age is 48.10 years with a standard deviation of 19.491.

The most common indications were IV medications with 160 responses (56.1%), followed by reperfusion due to hypovolemia/rehydration (76, 26.7%), Transfusion of blood and related products (26, 9.1%), and procedures requiring IV access (18, 6.3%). Indications are given in Graph I below.

Graph I: Indications of PIVC insertion.

Contraindications encountered during PIVC insertion were also assessed and are shown below in Table I.

Table I: Contraindications encountered during PIVC insertion

Contraindications encountered during PIVC insertion			
Presence of Edema	Presence of infection close to the insertion site.	Presence of an AV fistula	No contraindications
34 (12.1%)	32 (11.4%)	9 (3.5%)	205 (73%)

The pie chart below shows the staff involved in cannula insertion, with 262 (93.6%) nurses, 16 (5.7%) paramedical staff, and 2 (0.7%) doctors.

Pie Chart I: Staff involved in PIVC insertion.

Table II presents the various quality measures undertaken during the insertion of PIVC. Table II: Quality

measure during PIVC insertion.

Practice Measures	Yes	No
Informed Consent Taken	220 (78.6%)	60 (21.4%)
Procedure Explained to the Patient	170 (60.7%)	110 (39.3%)
The patient understood the Information	186 (66.4%)	94 (33.6%)
Proper Documentation of the Date/Time of Cannula Insertion	212 (75.7%)	68 (24.3%)
The patient was educated on Cannula Care	224 (80%)	56 (20%)
Aseptic Technique Followed for IV Cannulation	232 (82.9%)	48 (17.1%)
Pre-insertion check for appropriateness of Cannula Size and Site	250 (89.3%)	30 (10.7%)
Pre-Assessment for Infection, AV Fistula, or DVT (Lower Limb Insertion)	216 (77.1%)	64 (22.9%)
Proper Securing of IV Cannula	272 (97.1%)	8 (2.9%)
Documentation of Insertion Details (Aseptic Techniques, Dressing)	210 (75%)	70 (25%)
Regular Assessment and Flushing of IV Cannula	228 (81.4%)	52 (18.6%)

Table III shows the circumstances for PIVC removal. Table II: Quality

measure during PIVC insertion.

Circumstances for IVC removal	Frequency	Percentage
Redness and swelling	58	21%
Signs of Infection	8	3%
Patient Discharged	138	49%
Re-sited at 72 hours	60	21%
Adherence to the Aseptic technique is unknown	16	6%

Pie chart II further highlights the number of cannulation attempts, with 206 (73.6%) patients requiring one attempt and 74 (26.4%) requiring more than one attempt. Table IV shows the duration for which the IV cannula remained in place.

Pie Chart II: Number of cannulation attempts

Table IV: Duration of IV cannula

Duration of IV Cannula	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 24 hours	12	4.3%
24-48 hours	126	45%
Up to 72 hours	97	34.6%
More than 72 hours	45	16.1%

The frequency of post-removal IV cannula assessment (48 hours later) was 68 (24.3%). However, 212 (75.7%) cases were not assessed 48 hours post-removal.

Chi-square tests were conducted to compare different variables. They showed a significant association between the site and size appropriateness of the cannula before insertion and the number of cannulation attempts, with a p-value of <0.05 and a degree of freedom of 1.

Table V: Chi-Square analysis of site and size appropriateness of cannula before insertion and number of cannulation attempts.

Size and Site of Cannula Appropriate	No. of cannulation attempts		
	One	More than one	Total
Yes	195	55	250
No	10	20	30
P value <0.05			

Chi-square analysis also revealed that the inserter has a significant influence on the success rate of IV cannulation. Nurses had the highest rate of successful first-attempt insertions—p-value of 0.03 (degree of freedom: 2) as shown in Table VI. Table VII also shows the relation between the aseptic technique and those who passed the PIVC.

Table VI: Practitioner inserting cannula in relation to the success of cannulation

	One attempt	More than one attempt	Total
Doctor	1	1	2
Nurse	198	64	262
Paramedical Staff	6	10	16
Total	205	75	280
P value 0.03			

Table VII: Proper Aseptic technique and who passed PIVC.

Who passed PIVC	Aseptic Technique		
	Yes	No	Total
Doctor	1	1	2
Nurse	222	40	262
Paramedical Staff	9	7	16
P value 0.06			

However, no significant relationship (chi-square p-value of 0.06) was found between the use of proper aseptic technique and who passed the PIVC, as shown in Table VII.

Discussion

This study assesses the current state of practice regarding PIVC placement methods and care. The study revealed a high rate of undocumented cases (24%) with respect to documentation of the date and time of cannula insertion. This is comparable to another study, which showed only 86% compliance with respect to PIVC documentation [12]. Improvement regarding the documentation of PIVC-related details can help highlight adherence to guidelines and providing the details regarding insertion and removal may allow targeted solutions to any complications that may arise [12].

Nurses comprised 93.6% of the healthcare practitioners involved in the insertion of a PIVC. Other studies also show similar results, indicating more than 71% of the PIVC insertions and post-nurses carried out insertion care [9]. This further emphasizes the importance of prioritizing structural education programs and simulation-based training of nurses, all of which can reduce PIVC complication rates and increase insertion success [13].

After insertion the majority of cannulas 18.6% were not regularly assessed and flushed. This may lead to blockage and extravasation of cannula contents going undiscovered and can contribute to a higher rate of PIVC related complications [14]. Studies in South Asia showed that poor nursing care could increase the incidence of PIVC related infections by seven times [9].

This study also indicates that 73.6% of patients required only one successful attempt at cannulation, while 26.4% required more than one attempt. This is comparable to another study which reported that 12-26% of adults required more than one attempt at PIVC insertion for it to be successful [15]. An increasing number of failed attempts can increase vessel trauma and thus lead to higher rates of PIVC failure and replacement with subsequent complications [6].

According to the findings of this study, even though 78.6% of the practitioners obtained informed consent from the patient before inserting a PIVC, only 60% actually explained the procedure to the patient in detail. This indicates a potential lack of effective communication. This communication gap may lead to increased patient anxiety since many patients perceive the PIVC insertion process to be uncomfortable and painful. This is in contrast with another study, which showed informed consent was obtained from 95% of the patients [16]. Insufficient interactions between the patients and healthcare practitioners or lack of adherence to current training protocols may explain this difference [17]. To address the challenges associated with informed consent, we recommend that hospitals prioritize this process and actively oversee its implementation in clinical practice [17].

82.9% of practitioners followed the aseptic technique when inserting a cannula, and 89.3% did pre insertion checks for cannula size and site. This is similar to a study conducted in Nepal, which showed that 99.5% of the respondents maintained an aseptic technique for cannula insertion and maintenance [18]. Recommendations to reduce the risk of PIVC-related infections include hand hygiene before catheter insertion and aseptic and non-touch techniques of catheter maintenance and handling [3].

Chi-square analysis revealed that using an appropriately sized cannula would result in a significantly lower number of cannulation attempts [11]. This is comparable to another study which also reports higher first-attempt cannulation success depending on size and site of the PIVC [11]. The definition of an ‘appropriate’ sized cannula, however may vary as using a catheter size too small or too large can result in cannulation failure. Hence, an optimal catheter-to-vein ratio is needed for a successful cannulation [19]. A catheter-to-vein ratio cut-off of 0.41 is usually optimal [19]. More than one cannulation attempt is a very well-recognized cause of PIVC-associated complications [20].

The results of this study also reveal an insignificant chi-square value of 0.06 when relating adherence to aseptic technique and the healthcare practitioner who passed the PIVC. This borderline value is in contrast with a study conducted in Saudi Arabia, in which nurses demonstrated higher compliance with aseptic techniques, particularly with regard to hand hygiene [21]. This shows the need to highlight the clinical importance of aseptic PIVC insertion and the complications that can result from not doing so, as healthcare providers often underestimate them [3]. Training and education of all healthcare practitioners with respect to aseptic PIVC insertion is required [22].

A Limitation of this study includes reliance on self-reported data from the nurses, which may be subject to recall bias or social desirability bias.

Conclusion

This study was undertaken to gain a deeper understanding of the current clinical environment for peripheral intravenous catheter insertion and care, and to identify issues or gaps that clinical experts may address during a clinical roundtable. There needs to be the development of a hospital clinical care standard that will assist in bringing clinicians and health services together to agree on the way forward to improve outcomes for all patients who rely on safe and effective vascular access for the delivery of vital medical treatment.

Declarations

Funding:

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Review Board of Benazir Bhutto Hospital and Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar under reference numbers 6295 and 653. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Author Contributions

Imad Majeed: Conceptualization, data collection, manuscript drafting
 Shafaq Saleem: Statistical analysis, methodology review, Manuscript editing.
 Maaz Ullah: Data Collection, Manuscript Drafting.
 Arooba Khan: Manuscript editing, supervision.
 Mahnoor Khatak: Data Collection, Manuscript Drafting.
 Sara Rahman: Manuscript editing, supervision.
 Muhammad Haroon: Manuscript editing, supervision.
 Lubna Meraj: Supervision and Review
 All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Reference

1. Kaphan K, Auypornsakul S, Somno J, Wongwattananan W, Jamsittikul K, Baicha W, Somsri S, Sawatrak T. The prevalence and associated factors of peripheral intravenous complications in a Thai hospital. *Journal of Infusion Nursing*. 2024 Mar 1;47(2):120-31.
2. Marsh N, Larsen EN, Ullman AJ, Mihala G, Cooke M, Chopra V, Ray-Barruel G, Rickard CM. Peripheral intravenous catheter infection and failure: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 2024 Mar 1;151:104673.
3. Zingg W, Barton A, Bitmead J, Eggimann P, Pujol M, Simon A, Tatzel J. Best practice in the use of peripheral venous catheters: a scoping review and expert consensus. *Infection prevention in practice*. 2023 Jun 1;5(2):100271.
4. Berger I, Cohen T, Rahmani E, Levy I, Lowenthal A, Levinsky Y, Goldberg L, Marcus N, Kropach N, Ben-Zvi H, Chodik G. Peripheral venous catheter-related bloodstream infections in hospitalized children: the role of gram-negative bacteria. *The Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal*. 2021 Nov 1;40(11):e395-9.
5. Pittiruti M, Van Boxtel T, Scoppettuolo G, Carr P, Konstantinou E, Ortiz Miluy G, Lamperti M, Goossens GA, Simcock L, Dupont C, Inwood S. European recommendations on the proper indication and use of peripheral venous access devices (the ERPIUP consensus): a WoCoVA project. *The journal of vascular access*. 2023 Jan;24(1):165-82.
6. Hu AZ, Yin XY, Luo C, Lu LA, Lai HL, Liu L. Impact of a WeChat-based intervention on nurses knowledge and practice in peripheral venous catheter insertion. *Scientific Reports*. 2025 May 25;15(1):1-8.
7. DeVries M, Scott N. Keeping patients safer: reviewing predictors of success and failure of short peripheral intravenous catheters. *Journal of Infusion Nursing*. 2022 Jul 1;45(4):210-9.
8. Kefale D, Baih SZ, Ayenew YE. Practice towards care and maintenance of peripheral intravenous cannula among nurses and midwives in teaching hospitals, Amhara, Ethiopia. *The Pan African Medical Journal*. 2024 Aug 9;48:166.
9. Dessalegn A, Ali MS, Yohannes S, Tamir Y, Mulatu S, Zewdie A. Knowledge, practice and associated factors towards intravenous cannula-related infection prevention among nurses working at Northwest Amhara Regional State Comprehensive Specialized Hospitals, Ethiopia. *BMC nursing*. 2024 Mar 11;23(1):168.
10. Yaqoob M, Masih S, Rasheed A, Shah Y, Uddin N, Siddiqui F, Rehan M, Khan RA, Ahmed F, Rehan M, Qasim R. Peripheral intravenous catheter-induced phlebitis in a tertiary hospital of Karachi: a cohort study. *British Journal of Nursing*. 2024 Jul 18;33(14):S30-IV.
11. Mörgeli R, Schmidt K, Neumann T, Kruppa J, Föhring U, Hofmann P, Rosenberger P, Falk E, Boemke W, Spies C. A comparison of first-attempt cannulation success of peripheral venous catheter systems with and without wings and injection ports in surgical patients—a randomized trial. *BMC anesthesiology*. 2022 Mar 31;22(1):88.
12. Bahl A, Mielke N, Johnson S. Reliability and compliance of peripheral intravenous catheter documentation: A prospective observational study. *The journal of vascular access*. 2024 Jan;25(1):89-93.
13. Mannari J, Soni PA. Optimizing Peripheral Intravenous Catheter Outcomes: A Systematic Meta-Analysis of Educational Innovations, Technological Advancements, and Protocol-Based Strategies. *Journal of Radiology Nursing*. 2025 Mar 4.
14. Billingham MJ, Mittal R. Peripheral venous extravasation injury. *BJA education*. 2023 Feb 1;23(2):42-5.
15. Prasad RO, Chew T, Giri JR, Hoerauf K. Patient experience with vascular access management informs satisfaction with overall hospitalization experience. *Journal of Infusion Nursing*. 2022 Mar 1;45(2):95-103.
16. Santos-Costa P, Paiva-Santos F, Sousa LB, Bernardes RA, Ventura F, Fearnley WD, Salgueiro-Oliveira A, Parreira P, Vieira M, Graveto J. Nurses' practices in the peripheral intravenous catheterization of adult oncology patients: A mix-method study. *Journal of personalized medicine*. 2022 Jan 24;12(2):151.
17. Gong N, Zhou Y, Cheng Y, Chen X, Li X, Wang X, Chen G, Chen J, Meng H, Zhang M. Practice of informed consent in Guangdong, China: a qualitative study from the perspective of in-hospital patients. *BMJ open*. 2018 Oct 1;8(10):e020658.

18. Osti C, Khadka M, Wosti D, Gurung G, Zhao Q. Knowledge and practice towards care and maintenance of peripheral intravenous cannula among nurses in Chitwan Medical College Teaching Hospital, Nepal. *Nursing open*. 2019 Jul;6(3):1006-12.
19. van Loon FH, Korsten HH, Dierick-van Daele AT, Bouwman AR. The impact of the catheter to vein ratio on peripheral intravenous cannulation success, a post-hoc analyses. *PLoS One*. 2021 May 24;16(5):e0252166.
20. Scudder C, Haskey E, Maund V, Allerton F, Heard C, O'Donnell C, Davison K, Hertel C, Booth E, Lawrence S, Dever E. Placement Management And Complications Associated With Peripheral Intravenous Catheter Use In UK Small Animal Practice.
21. Almahmoud RS, Alfarhan MA, Alanazi WM, Alhamidy FK, Balkhy HH, Alshamrani M, El-Saed A, Sairafi BA, Bahron SA. Assessment knowledge and practices of central line insertion and maintenance in adult intensive care units at a tertiary care hospital in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Infection and Public Health*. 2020 Nov 1;13(11):1694-8.
22. Ferdianingsih T, Efendi D, Widiastuti IA. Factors influencing nurse compliance in maintaining aseptic technique in the insertion of peripheral intravenous access in neonates. *Journal of Neonatal Nursing*. 2023 Jun 1;29(3):490-5.